

Supplementary information to Clinical & Experimental Allergy article:

A new vicilin-like allergen in hazelnut giving rise to a spectrum of IgE binding low molecular weight N-terminal fragments

Lars Mattsson, Marie Holmqvist, Helena Porsch, Håkan Larsson, Bo Pontoppidan, Andre Valcour, Jonas Lidholm

Figure S1. Comparison of IgE antibody binding to a natural vicilin_N preparation from hazelnut and a recombinant protein comprising five selected vicilin_N peptide units of Cor a 16 (#1, #2, #3, #5 and #10) in 11 sera of hazelnut allergic subjects sensitized to hazelnut storage proteins. To visualize all observations, values <0.1 kU_A/L were set to 0.1 kU_A/L. Hatched vertical and horizontal lines indicate the 0.35 kU_A/L level and hatched diagonal line the 1:1 slope.